

1. **Select** a suitable data repository. You can find one with the UU repository finder: tools.uu.nl/repository-decision-tool/.

2. **Create** a dataset at the data repository.

3. **Upload** your data.

Start here

Findability

- Provide as much **descriptive metadata** about your dataset as possible.
- Write an **abstract** that describes both your dataset and the research topic.
- Use **keywords** common in your research domain.
- If possible, add your **ORCID ID** to the author field.
 - You don't have an **ORCID** yet? Go to orcid.org and sign up!
- A **DOI** will be provided by the data repository. Utilize this DOI to **share** your dataset.
- Check if a **controlled vocabulary** is available for your domain. Utilize this if applicable or contact your research data manager.
- Promote** your dataset in social media and your research community.

Accessibility

- Does your dataset consist of **privacy sensitive data** or other data that cannot be disclosed?

README template on the back!

Interoperability

- Store your data in a **format** that is, preferably:
 - Open
 - Commonly used
 - Supported by open source software

Add the following information to your **README file**:

- An **overview** of the files and folders in the dataset.
- Describe what **kind of file** they are (the format).
- Describe **file naming conventions** if relevant/needed.
- Describe required or preferred **software** to open or process the data.
- Add a **codebook** with data level metadata. This involves a description of your variables and outcome values.

Reusability

- Publish your dataset under a **license**. Do you want to publish your data fully **open** or with (some) **restrictions**?

Add the following information to your **README file**:

- Provide **documentation** on your **data** and your **data collection**.
- Provide **examples** on how to re-use your data, e.g. a script to load your data.

Interested in more on FAIR data?

Visit uu.nl/rdm for guides, workshops, and walk-in hours. Or contact our experts at info.rdm@uu.nl.

Your dataset is now FAIR and ready to be published!

README template

README.md

Title of your dataset

In this section, provide an overview of your dataset and describe the project and research questions in which the dataset was collected. Explain the data collection methods. Highlight the purpose, scope, and potential uses of your dataset.

Prerequisites

Include any necessary prerequisites for using your dataset, such as specific software or hardware requirements. Provide clear instructions for how to access or download your data files.

Contents

Describe the organization of your data package, including the contents of each folder and the files it contains. Provide and explain the naming convention used for the files in your dataset. Also describe the file format(s) used in your dataset and the software required to open them.

Codebook

Provide a codebook that explains the variables in your dataset. This is particularly important for tabular data, but it is useful for any other type of file as well. Include at least the variable name, a brief description, and the data type.

License

Include a license that allows others to use and share your work. Consider using an open data license, such as a Creative Commons License.

For example: This work is licensed under a CC BY 4.0.

Citation (optional)

Provide clear instructions on how to cite your dataset or related publications in a research paper or publication.

Contact

Include contact information for questions, feedback and suggestions about your dataset.

Interested in more on writing a README?

Visit uu.nl/rdm for guides, workshops, and walk-in hours. Or contact our experts at info.rdm@uu.nl.

Check out the
extended version:

<https://bit.ly/FAIR-Data-Readme>

